

Evaluation of field condition by using smart rice transplanter

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Abstract

Lodging of rice has become a big problem for large scale farmer during harvesting season. Investigating topsoil depth (TD) and apparent electrical conductivity (EC_a) of paddy field will be the key to solve this problem. In this study, we developed smart rice transplanter, which could measure TD and EC_a . The TD was measured by ultrasonic distance sensor (USS). The EC_a was measured by soil electrical conductivity sensor (ECS). We defined that the EC_a measured by ECS was soil fertility value (SFV). Each sensor could obtain data every one second. As a result of field test in 2016, total 740,000 of datasets were collected from 50ha paddy. The average of the TD was 19.8 cm while the maximum, minimum, and standard deviation (SD) of TD were 68.47, 7.45 and 6.62 cm respectively. The average of the SFV was 1.04 mS/cm while the maximum, minimum, and SD of SFV were 9.57, 0.07 and 0.68 mS/cm respectively. The result also revealed that high TD was observed in heading area due to machine turning inside the field. In this study, TD and SFV were also applied for variable rate fertilizer application. We designed variable rate ratio with 4 levels. Level 1 where high TD zone reduced by 30%. Level 2 where high SFV zone reduced by 20%. Level 3 where a little high SFV zone reduced by 10%. Level 4 where the other zone fertilized conventional amount. As a result, the smart rice transplanter saved 20% of fertilizer than conventional application.

Introduction

The most promising approach for attaining sustainable agriculture, and thereby keeping agricultural productivity with population growth, is precision agriculture (Corwin et al., 2005). In the research field of precision agriculture, the idea of site-specific management is important. Site-specific management is the management of agricultural crops at a spatial scale smaller than that of the whole field (Plant, 2001).

In Japan, precision agriculture for rice production has been studied for two decade. One of the objectives of those studies is mitigation of lodging. A large-scale producer have got more that they were entrusted with others paddy field in recent years. Due to the increase of cultivation area, efficient harvest is required. Lodging position takes more time to harvest compared to non-lodging one. Suitable period for rice harvest is about a week, and interruption due to the lodging condition became a major problem. Lodging might also lead to a decrease in the percentage of ripe grains or associated with low grain quality (Toriyama et al. 2003). The cause of lodging is excessive application of nitrogen fertilizer. It promotes hypertrophy of heads of rice. As a result, rice becomes liable to fall down.

In order to prevent rice from lodging, variable rate fertilizer application (VRA) based on map delineating the spatial variations can be considered as one of option. Therefore, we proposed the system performing soil sensing and VRA during rice transplanting.

In agriculture, apparent electrical conductivity (EC_a) measurement has used for direct mapping of soil spatial variation. EC_a measurement is the technology that has become an invaluable tool for identifying the soil physicochemical properties influencing crop yield patterns and for establishing the spatial variation of these soil properties (Corwin et al., 2003).

Piikki et al. (2013) fused EC_a data got by on EM38-MK2 with gamma ray spectrometry, elevation and digital numbers of an aerial photo for topsoil clay mapping. Sudduth et al. (2013) modeled soil electrical conductivity–depth relationships with EC_a data from DUALEM-2S and Veris2000XA.

As for soil sensor for paddy field, however, there has been little research investigation. Especially, there is no report available in terms of soil sensor for paddy flood condition (Morimoto et al., 2013). Therefore, we developed the soil electrical conductivity sensor (ECS) for measuring EC_a during the rice transplanting in real time.

Various studies have been done on VRA. Fleming et al. (2004) delineated management zone for VRA using apparent electrical conductivity and aerial photograph. Ostergaard (1997) developed management zones for variable rate N application based on soil type, yield, topography, aerial photos, and producer experience. In his study, five experiment fields were divided into 12 to 17 management zones. They found a \$15 to \$35 /ha economic advantage using variable rate N application.

The objectives of this research are 1) to confirmation the usefulness of topsoil depth (TD) and soil fertility value (SFV) as soil evaluation parameter, 2) to investigate temporal spatial variations for each field, and 3) to perform VRA while sensing.

Materials and methods

1. Topsoil depth measurement

Smart rice transplanter (SRT) is 8 rows type rice transplanter (NP80, Iseki). Topsoil depth (TD) was measured by ultrasonic distance sensor (USS). A couple of USS (E4PA-LS200-MI-N, Omron) set in front of the rice transplanter at a height of 850mm from the ground, as shown in Fig. 1 (a). The USS was affected by ambient temperature (i.e. $\pm 1\%$ F.S. (full scale: 2m) in the temperature range of -10 to 55 °C), but this specification could be acceptable for TD measurement. USS measured the distance to the soil surface, TD was calculated from a fixed height (i.e. 850mm) minus the average of two sensor data was shown in Fig.1 (b) and given by Eq. 1.

Equation.1

where D_{left} and D_{right} are distance from left and right sensor to soil surface (mm), respectively.

USS could be measured with 5Hz interval, provided average data per 5 datasets. USS could be measured in the same state during rice transplanting because soil surface is flattened by puddling before rice planting.

Figure 1. Topsoil depth (TD) measurement system (a) photo of ultrasonic sensor (b) schematic diagram of topsoil depth sensing

2. Soil electrical conductivity sensor

The soil electrical conductivity sensor (ECS) could measure bulk electrical conductivity (EC_{bulk}) during the rice transplanting. ECS was a couple of wheel type electrodes stainless steel sensor as shown in Fig. 2 (a). Electrodes were attached to the front wheel. The diameter and width of the ECS were 53cm and 5cm, respectively. The two electrodes of the ECS were maintained at 1.1m during rice transplanting. Alternative current of 1kHz frequency was flowing between front wheels in soil as shown in Fig. 2 (b).

Figure 2. Soil electrical conductivity sensor (a) photo of electrode (b) schematic diagram
 EC_{bulk} was affected by the soil moisture content and soil temperature. Since the moisture content of soil was close to 100% by puddling before rice transplanting, it could be measured without being affected by moisture content. To measure soil temperature, a platinum resistance thermometer (E52, Omron) was applied. This thermometer was installed under the float of the rice transplanter to measure soil surface temperature.

The interval of measurement was 1s and EC_{bulk} was compensated to 25°C by using Eq. 2. Temperature-compensated EC_{bulk} was defined as apparent electrical conductivity (EC_a) for further research.

Equation.2

where t is soil surface temperature (°C), λ_{25} is EC_a at 25°C (mS), and λ_t is bulk electrical conductivity (mS).

3. Soil fertility value

The ECS area of underground increases as the TD value increase was shown in Fig. 3. It was necessary to obtain electrical conductivity data not affected by TD value. Soil fertility value (SFV) was defined as a new soil parameter for field evaluation. As a preliminary test, we investigated the relationship between TD and EC_a . The EC_a with TD of 10 to 30 was measured with ECS in four EC conditions (i.e. 0.3, 0.4, 0.6, 0.7 mS/cm) by using water as shown in Fig. 4. The temperature condition during this preliminary test was 17.9 °C. Since it was found from the test results that there was a strong correlation between the TD and the EC_a , we concluded that the SFV was determined as the EC_a per unit TD as explained by Eq. 3.

Figure 3. Diagram of the difference in sensing area

Equation.3

where λ_{25} is EC_a at 25 °C (mS), TD is topsoil depth (cm).

4. Variable rate fertilizer application

SRT performed variable rate fertilizer application (VRA) during rice transplanting. Crop yield increases with high TD (Thompson et al., 1991). We designed variable rate ratio (VRR) with 4 levels. Level 1 was high TD zone where the TD value is above average plus standard deviation (SD). Level 2 was high SFV zone where the SFV value is above average plus SD. Level 3 is a little high SFV zone where the SFV value is above average and below average plus SD. Level 4 is the other zone. In this study, we set to reduce VRR Level 1, 2, 3 respectively by 30%, 20%, 10%. Level 4 fertilized conventional amount. This algorithm was shown by Fig. 5. 4 levels were determined from last transplanting field's data. Since the heading area had high TD due to machine turning, VRA didn't use dataset there. If SD of TD is less than 3cm, SD was set to 3cm unified.

Figure 4. Relationship between topsoil depth and apparent electrical conductivity in EC condition (i.e. 0.3, 0.4, 0.6, 0.7 mS/cm)

Figure 5. Algorithm of variable rate fertilizer application

5. Soil sampling

From TD, SFV and VRR, we created map for each field. With reference to the created SFV map, soil sampling was performed and analysis was made at each point from the high SFV point and the low SFV point. We decided 1m² sampling points from the map and randomly collected 5sets of soil sample from them. The soil was evenly sampled to a depth of 10cm. The soil samples were dried at 60C° for 24 hours or more and EC and Total-Nitrogen (T-N) content were measured. 100g of distilled water was added to 20g of dry soil, and after shaking for 1 hour, EC was measured with an electrical conductivity meter (CM20A, TOA). T-N content was measured from 0.5g of dry soil using a C/N coder (JM1000CN, J SCIENCE LAB).

6. Experimental field

The study was conducted on total 50ha paddy in Takemoto farm (36.43° N, 136.50° E) and Agricultural Corporation One (36.64° N, 136.69° E). These fields had been managed by large-scale producer. Field tests were conducted from April 25 to May 20, 2016. The study procedure were: 1) moving on planting line while only measuring data; 2) starting transplanting on next line; and then, 3) starting VRA on next line, as shown by Fig. 6. The distance in the vertical direction was calculated from the position data of Step.1 and Step.2 as explained by Eq. 4.

Figure 6. Rice transplanting process

Equation.4

where L_a is distance of planting line (m), L_1 and L_2 are distance measured in Step.1 and Step.2 (m), respectively.

The position data were measured by DGPS (A100, Hemisphere; stable accuracy 0.6m). From the calculated distance, it is decided that the measurement range of data to be used for VRA is minus 3m on both sides of the heading area.

Results and discussion

1. Sensor data

As a result of field test in 2016, total 740,000 of datasets were collected from 50ha paddy. Statistical data of each soil parameter was shown in Table 1. Since high TD value was observed in heading area and discrimination of the heading area could be done, it was considered that the TD had utility as soil evaluation parameter as shown in Fig. 7. The TD and SFV were soil property with temporal spatial variation. Therefore, it is necessary to continue the measurement in the future. The result of soil temperature histogram was shown in Fig. 8. Since soil temperature difference were observed for each field and temporal variation of soil temperature during transplanting due to sunlight were observed in the field, it was considered important to measure the soil temperature in SRT in real-time.

Figure 7. TD, SFV and variable rate ratio map of two fields from smart rice transplanter

Figure 8. Histogram of soil surface temperature

Table 1. Characteristics of topsoil depth, soil fertility value and temperature

	Max	Min	Ave	SD
Topsoil depth (cm)	68.5	7.45	19.8	6.62
Soil fertility value (mS/cm)	9.57	0.07	1.04	0.68
Soil temperature (°C)	40.5	9.95	24.4	5.16

2. Sampling data

As a result of the sampling survey in 2016, 34 samples were obtained in total of high SFV points and low SFV points. Statistical data of each SFV point was shown in Table 2. In EC, everything except the minimum was EC_h slightly higher than EC_l. In T-N, everything was T-N_h slightly higher than T-N_l. Since the range of each piece of data measured by SRT was very small, the sampling point could not be defined to be accurate.

Table 2. Characteristics of electrical conductivity and Total-Nitrogen content

	Max	Min	Ave	SD
EC _h (mS/cm)	0.115	0.063	0.088	0.017
EC _l (mS/cm)	0.112	0.069	0.087	0.012
T-N _h (mg/100g)	0.274	0.211	0.237	0.021
T-N _l (mg/100g)	0.262	0.202	0.230	0.019

3. Variable rate fertilizer application

Application maps created by VRR data like TD and SFV maps was shown in Fig. 7. Comparing the three data maps, it was confirmed that the VRR was changed for each TD and SFV data. By collecting VRR data every year, it will be possible to apply VRA suitable for soil properties and weather condition for each year. As a result of all the rice transplanting tests finished in 2016, SRT saved 20% of fertilizer than conventional application. We could not observe whether lodging was able to be relieved in this study. In the future, in addition to VRA area, conventional application area is needed to compare the amount of lodging.

Conclusions

In this paper, we proposed new evaluation system of soil condition and variable rate fertilizer application system by smart rice transplanter and presented experimental results. In the state of puddling before rice planting, sensing by ultrasonic distance sensor and soil electrical conductivity sensor was suitable. Based on the measured data, maps were created for each field and for each type of data. Comparing the maps, a difference of soil spatial variation was clearly seen for each field. By continuing the measurement in the future, temporal variation should also be confirmed. Variable rate fertilizer application was done using the average and standard deviation of topsoil depth and soil fertility value. Accurate application corresponding to sensing data was able to be done. By providing the conventional application area, we will be able to see the difference in the amount of lodging.

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